

An introduction to Humanitarian assistance: India's policy and practice for humanitarian aid

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Abstract

Humanitarian assistance has attracted the attention of the global community in recent years and the conceptual framework for participation in the humanitarian assistance operations is gaining increasing urgency among policy makers of the world. While the humanitarian gesture – the will to relieve the suffering of others- is centuries old and genuinely global, has been present in various forms throughout the human civilisation often in the form of food or material aid providing during famine, drought or natural disaster. With the end of Cold War, both the concept and the practice of the humanitarian assistance has significantly changed due to rising armed and ethnic conflicts, which offer much broader and long term objectives, such as development and peace. After the end of cold war Humanitarian assistance has emerged as an important mission for major militaries around the world and the mission that was largely left to the organisations such as the International Red Cross has now become an important part of the security agenda of nations with significant military capability. Since independence from Britain, which coincided with the partition of the subcontinent, India has come to the aid of people in need. Due to the significant expansion of the Indian economy from the last decades, the availability of greater financial resources in hand and a sense of growing regional and international responsibilities, India has revived and rejuvenated its tradition of giving humanitarian assistance. Although not formulated in policy, India's approach to Humanitarian assistance is derived from set of principles and priorities derived from the core values of its foreign policy. The purpose of the paper is to provide an introduction to the emergence of the international humanitarian assistance system with a review of the principles of humanitarian assistance. The paper also focuses on India's conception of humanitarian assistance and its underlying principles, motives and priorities for providing humanitarian assistance.

Keywords: Humanitarian assistance, aid, Western Donors, aid, humanitarianism, United Nations, India, Sri Lanka, , Afghanistan,

History and principles of humanitarian Action: Challenges and Dilemmas

The origin of modern humanitarianism is almost always placed in 1859, when the young Swiss entrepreneur Henri Dunant witnessed the Battle of Solferino. Outraged and shocked by the terrible conditions suffered by the wounded fighters left on the battlefield decided to seek help and medical

assistance for the wounded and sick soldiers with the help of local villagers.ⁱ Back to his home in Geneva, he wrote a book (*A Memory of Solferino*, 1862) where he proclaimed that all the nations should establish voluntary societies to assist and care for all individuals who are injured, wounded and sick in war.ⁱⁱ He proposed that these societies should have an “international principle, sanctioned by the convention inviolate in character” that would support the creation and protection of these societies by all states signatories of such conventionⁱⁱⁱ.

In 1862, Dunant’s initiative, along with Gustave Moynier, President of the Public Welfare Geneva Society, and General Dufour, created a committee aimed at guaranteeing medical care and assistance to those involved in war. At a conference in Geneva in 1863, delegates from 17 countries established the International Committee for Relief to the Wounded, which later became the International Committee of the Red Cross (ICRC).^{iv} The ICRC is closely related to the birth of International Humanitarian Law (IHL) and is also at the origin of the humanitarian principles of humanity, impartiality, neutrality and independence. The Red Cross Movement marked the emergency of international humanitarian non-governmental organisations throughout the twenty century and started out by providing assistance in times of war. This is how different non-governmental organisations like Save the Children (1919), Oxfam (1942) or CARE (1945) were born.

The end of the world war second marked the creation of the United Nations, one of the main players in the humanitarian system. Three of the five UN agencies having humanitarian mandate were created out of the concerns for the people affected by the scourge of war and oppression: The UN Children’s Fund (UNICEF, 1946) was originally created to respond to the needs of Europe’s war-affected children, while the UN Relief and Works Agency for Palestinian Refugees (UNRWA, 1950) and the UN High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR, 1951) were established for refugees fleeing conflict and persecution.^v

The Nigeria-Biafra war marked another evolution in the humanitarian system: the emergence of a new humanitarianism with an independent political edge. The contentious problems faced by the humanitarian workers in Biafra led to the birth of several new humanitarian agencies mostly notably MSF (Medecins Sans Frontiers) and Concern. These two organisations distanced themselves from the neutral attitude of the ICRC both responding to crisis and advocating for those caught in them. Furthermore the conflicts due to cold war in 1970s and 1980s marked the establishment of a new generation of NGOs such as ACF (Action Contre La Faim) in France, Merlin in the UK, and GOAL in Ireland.^{vi}

With the end of the cold war and emergence of the new world order, characterised by the geopolitical change, growing number of violent ethnic conflicts and crisis, both the concept and the practice of the humanitarian enterprise has significantly changed. The three major events mostly internal and complex in the first half of the 1990s: the Balkans wars (Especially Bosnia), the civil war and famine in Somalia and the Rwanda genocide and the subsequent refugee crisis particularly in Goma witnessed upheavals in the humanitarian system. The responses to these complex humanitarian crises and conflicts were frequently confused and ill-conceived, reflecting an international community concerned with the alleviation of human suffering worldwide but, at the same time, ill-prepared and sharing very different interests and priorities.^{vii}

As a result, classical humanitarian action has received extreme criticism for responses in these new conflict scenarios. According to its critics, both at the academic and practical level, these actions emphasized the ineffectiveness and lack of professional characteristic of classical humanitarian organizations that fed and perpetuated conflicts and crises through their misuse of aid and poor resource distribution.^{viii} In addition the 1990s decade witnessed the institutionalization of humanitarian assistance, with the creation of main stakeholders such United Nations Department of Humanitarian Affairs (which in 1998 became OCHA) and the office of Commission's European Community Humanitarian Office (ECHO), the main humanitarian donor to date.

Claiming to correct the mistakes of the past and representing a radical rupture with the classic conception of humanitarian assistance, a multi-dimensional conception of humanitarianism emerged. The movement gained importance and was adopted by most donor governments, multilateral agencies and many NGOs. This so-called "new humanitarianism" clearly challenged the classic paradigm. Given the change in conflict and post-conflict circumstances, the traditional objectives of saving lives and relieving human suffering were insufficient and merely temporary. The basic idea was that humanitarian assistance should have longer-term objectives such as peace building, human rights protection and promotion and, in a last stage, peace.^{ix}

With the end of the cold war conflicts were no longer between states but rather within states themselves, lead massive displacement of civilians and instability within the entire regions. The UN Security Council since 1991 started to demand international access to displaced and other population affected by conflict and massive human rights abuse, sometimes authorising the use of force to guarantee the delivery of aid. As a response to violent conflicts involving gross violations of human rights that threatened to generate wider instability, the requirements of security had begun to include the protection

of communities and individuals from internal violence. After the end of the bipolarity the concepts of impartiality and neutrality became rather unclear and were often misunderstood.

Indeed, for the last years, action and allocation of funds into some crises or others has not only been decided according to gravity of disasters or the needs of the affected populations, but also by the geopolitical and economic interests of the big donors and main political powers. The 9/11 events and the following western led war on terror were a clear proof of the fact. Some governments tried to use humanitarian aid as a strategic tool in their war terror.^x In the wake of 9/11 it became much more difficult to distinguish this agenda, and the mechanism by which it will be achieved, from the more politicized and contested security agenda of the global war on terror.^{xi} It became clear that the guiding principles of classical humanitarian action – humanity, impartiality, neutrality and independence within the framework of this ‘new humanitarianism,’ are progressively abandoned and replaced by other principles and priorities in these new contexts and follow a new, integrated agenda to respond to new types of violent conflicts and resulting humanitarian crisis.

Though progressively defended in theory and practice, especially by donor governments, the new humanitarianism raised various important ethical problems as it resulted in a distortion in the original essence of humanitarianism and limited independent and impartial humanitarian action.

This new framework of humanitarianism is also being questioned and challenged in its assumptions by various academics and practitioners due to the fact that decisions that had humanitarian implications were increasingly being taken on the basis of political criteria and interests instead of on the victims’ needs. It is exactly in this scenario of important changes that the first criticism to the ‘new humanitarianism’ arises focusing mainly on what were considered as its main risks and challenges: political use of humanitarian action, conditionality (mainly in terms of human rights conditions attached to aid); erosion of classical humanitarian principles and militarization^{xii}.

Indian Humanitarian assistance

Though humanitarian operations have only recently acquired international recognition but India has a long tradition of humanitarian assistance. Humanitarianism lies at the heart of Indian spiritual and cultural values. Islam and Sikhism all promote solidarity with the suffering and giving without expectations for return. The Hindu term daan, for example, emphasizes the self-less nature of giving. In fact, the sacred Hindu scripture Bhagavad Gita preaches that there should be no motive in charity and there should be no aim, direct or indirect. These spiritual traditions influence the humanitarian impulses

of Indian decision makers. India conceives humanitarian assistance as “extending sympathy” to the disaster-affected or as “a goodwill gesture”.

Infact since its independence from Britain, which coincided with the partition of the subcontinent, the country has come to the aid of people in need. Even there was broad consensus among the leaders of India soon after its independence that, despite the country’s developmental needs, it should not become overly dependent on foreign aid. Within few years after independence, India became home for thousands of Tibetan Refugees in 1959 led by their spiritual leader, the Dalai Lama and in 1970-71 when the Pakistan army cracked down on popular protests in East Bengal, India had to host nearly 10 million refugees.

During the Sri Lankan Civil War In 1987, India flew humanitarian assistance materials to civilians in the city of Jaffna, an act that could be viewed as one of the few humanitarian interventions worldwide. India has also received, and still hosts, large numbers of refugees from Tibet, Myanmar, Sri Lanka and Afghanistan, and has done so with little assistance from the UN refugee agency, UNHCR, or other international actors. Although India is not signatory to the 1951 Refugee Convention or its 1967 Protocol, and appears unlikely to ratify either, but its record of hosting and treating refugees is better than that of some countries who are signatories.^{xiii}

Indian armed forces play an important role in providing humanitarian assistance outside its own region. Not only that India is also among top Peacekeeping providers among the world and was third largest troop contributing country in 2014. It also has a long-standing Technical and Economic co-operation (ITEC) scheme, established in 1964 as a way to share Indian development knowledge and technical expertise with other poor countries through training and partnerships on a modest budget. ITEC is run by the Ministry of External Affairs and has four components: Training; projects and project related activities; deputation of Indian experts; and study tour. Thus, India is also a pioneer of the partnership and capacity-building model currently favoured by the international aid community^{xiv}.

Since the end of the cold war, the scale and frequency of India’s efforts to help those in distress have changed significantly. Today, as the world’s fastest growing economy, India has the means to contribute to international aid efforts more systematically. Although a large share of its population is still poor, and though huge income gaps characterize the Indian economy, India has come a long way; once dependent on Western aid, has emerged as one of the leading non-western donor of international assistance.

From 2001 onwards following the overthrow of Taliban, India has been one of the top five donors to Afghanistan. Although part of its soft power strategy, India’s humanitarian contribution to Afghanistan

is impressive. India runs one of the most successful post-conflict humanitarian projects in northern Sri Lanka, building housing for displaced Tamils. It has also rebuilt the railway line to Jaffna in the far north of that country. It is a major donor to other neighbours, Bhutan and Nepal, and it has dramatically increased its aid to sub-Saharan African countries over the past decade.^{xv} In 2017, General V.K. Singh, the then Minister of State for External Affairs informed that India had been a net donor in 2015-2016 by donating US\$ 1.1 billion as aid and is receiving only US\$ 300 million from foreign countries and global banks.

Due to the significant expansion of the Indian economy from the last decades, the availability of greater financial resources in hand and a sense of growing regional and international responsibilities, India has revived and rejuvenated its tradition of giving humanitarian assistance and this sensibility is seen in India's response to humanitarian crisis across the world, including the Hurricane Katrina in the United States in 2005 and the Fukushima disaster in Japan in 2011. India possesses strong sense of internationalism and brotherhood, has also began to support international organisations engaged in the humanitarian relief. The world Food Programme (WFP), the world's largest humanitarian organisation addressing hunger and promoting food security was a net provider of food to India until early 2000s acknowledged India as the 15th largest donor in 2006.

India always has shown a strong preference to share its expertise in disaster management with other developing countries, for example with Afghanistan, Pakistan and Guyana. Every year the Indian government manages with a large number of internal disasters and in response has developed a sophisticated disaster management system over the past decade and has also helped other South Asian countries in setting up similar systems. Decision makers of India aim to earn goodwill of foreign governments and local people affected by disasters by promoting a positive image of India in these countries.

The Indian government also launched a coordinating and monitoring body for Indian foreign assistance within the ministry of External affairs called the Development Partnership Administration (DPA). Aimed to evolve as a full-fledged aid agency, the formation of DPA is widely recognised as an encouraging step for the decentralised and fragmented Indian aid programme. India's Humanitarian assistance does not only goes to its immediate neighbours but also extended the reach of its assistance well beyond South Asia. The rise of India as a donor country in the less developed countries has augmented its humanitarian contributions. "India has the potential to match its global aspiration in humanitarian action. The country's reputed domestic disaster management and generous development budget would allow it for a more significant humanitarian engagement", wrote Andras Horvath of

Global Public Policy Institute in a research paper titled, “India as a Humanitarian Donor in the 21st Century: The seeds of more ambitious role”.

India’s conception of Humanitarian assistance: Motives and principles for providing relief

According to Claudia Meier and C.S.R Murthy, “The Indian government uses the terms “humanitarian assistance” or “disaster relief” to refer to activities that address human suffering caused by natural disasters like cyclones, droughts, earthquakes or floods. This definition is narrower than Western donors’ conception of humanitarian assistance, which also includes helping civilian populations affected by armed conflicts”. Indeed, over the years India has provided ample assistance to countries struck by natural disasters, but in reality its humanitarian outreach is not restricted to such emergencies – India has supplied the bulk of humanitarian assistance in two post-conflict situations, namely Afghanistan and Sri Lanka. India’s “disaster relief” rhetoric is possibly deliberate in order to avoid international political controversies associated with giving aid during civil war situations.^{xvi}

With respect to the separation between short-term relief and development assistance, Indian officials have only recently started to distinguish the two^{xvii}. In 2003, the government supplied Cambodia with indelible ink to support elections, an act that it categorized under “humanitarian aid”^{xviii}. Today, Indian decision makers use the same conceptual separation as Western donors, designating short-term assistance in the aftermath of disasters as humanitarian assistance and long-term assistance as development assistance.

According to the Indian self-conception, the central reasons for providing relief are a genuine desire to help countries in distress and a wish to foster friendly relations through the provision of such assistance. Although not formulated in policy, India’s approach to Humanitarian assistance is derived from set of principles and priorities derived from the core values of its foreign policy. The most important guiding principle is the emphasis on the centrality of territorial sovereignty and the principle of non-intervention in the internal affairs of state, which is an important legacy of the country’s struggle against the colonialism and the defining commitment of the non-alignment movement. Time and again the Indian representatives at the united nations insists that the humanitarian assistance or disaster relief must be provided only with the consent of the country affected and in principle on the basis of an appeal from the authorities of the affected country.

India even objected to the UN Secretary General’s call for granting relief organizations better access to disaster-affected populations^{xix}. Accordingly, India dispenses most assistance directly to the affected country’s government, a preference that reflects its interest to foster friendly relations.

In line with this view on sovereignty, India aims to provide assistance according to the requirements and needs as defined by the affected government, an approach that Indian decision makers have labelled “demand-driven” aid. Western donors define “demand-driven” aid differently in that they focus on the needs of the affected population. India criticizes aid from Western donors and organizations as “supply driven” and accuses them of carelessly providing aid. India strives to adopt a strictly non-political approach to humanitarian assistance, stressing that humanitarian aid should not be linked to political objectives and identifies humanitarian assistance from Western donors as political, for example in the case of the 2008 cyclone in Myanmar during which calls for regime change and humanitarian assistance were difficult to separate. As a result, India avoids the “donor” category and likes to categorise itself as “Partner” who wants to stand in solidarity with its sister developing countries in distress.

India also subscribes to the international humanitarian principles of universality, neutrality and impartiality. Furthermore; India emphasizes the importance of a smooth transition from immediate relief to the long term development phase. Indian decision makers highlight the importance of reaching the affected country promptly in case of natural disasters. This is as much a question of genuine concern as it is of visibility. India also receives international visibility when stressing that it was among the first countries to disburse aid to high-level emergencies, notably the 2004 Indian Ocean Tsunami and the 2010 Haiti earthquake.^{xx}

In 2009, the conflict in Palestine led India to provide humanitarian assistance to the Palestinian territories, and India also disbursed humanitarian aid to Tajikistan to avert famine there. Furthermore, in response to floods in 2010, India went ahead to provide humanitarian aid to Pakistan — a country with which it has fought three wars. These endeavours reflect not only India’s superior institutional capacity to respond to natural calamities, but also the necessary political commitment and diplomatic skill to act promptly and engage beyond India’s traditional neighbourhood. India is also expanding its development assistance to African countries beyond its traditional relationships within the Commonwealth in an effort to secure access to natural resources as well as serve its broader strategic aims. Through its state-owned companies, it has significantly increased oil imports from African countries.^{xxi}

If we look closely India’s humanitarian assistance strategy is also determined by the political factors for making good relations with other developing countries in order to gain support for permanent seat in the United Nations Security council and by economic factors to gain access to new markets and raw materials. India’s assistance effort is evidently involved into a larger set of foreign-policy goals as India wants to ensure secure sources of energy for its expanding economy, opening markets for India’s increasingly export-oriented industrial and service sectors, and bolstering geostrategic ties with key

neighbours. Due to India's status as an emerging economy, a consolidated democracy, Indian foreign assistance has great legitimacy in the eyes of other emerging countries - a legitimacy in clear contrast to that of China. It is this legitimacy that differentiates Indian development assistance and is likely to bolster its soft power^{xxii}. Though India's changing policy with regard to the receipt of aid marked these ideas that it considers receipt of aid as hindrance for its growing global aspiration and to play a greater global role. Though it is widely discussed that there is a policy in place since 2004, enunciated by the then Prime Minister Dr. Manmohan Singh, that not to accept foreign aid in times of natural disasters. There is another argument that India is more self-sufficient and hence does not need relief material to deal with natural disasters and calamities.

Conclusion

It may be concluded that with the end of Cold War, both the concept and the practice of the humanitarian assistance has significantly changed due to rising armed and ethnic conflicts, which offer much broader and long term objectives, such as development and peace. Though increasingly defended in theory and practice, especially by donor governments, the new humanitarianism raised various important ethical problems as it resulted in a distortion in the original essence of humanitarianism and limited independent and impartial humanitarian action. This new framework of humanitarianism is also being questioned and challenged in its assumptions by various academics and practitioners due to the fact that decisions that had humanitarian implications were increasingly being taken on the basis of political criteria and interests instead of on the victims' needs.

Since the independence of India from Britain, which coincided with the partition of the subcontinent, the country has come to the aid of people in need. Although not formulated in policy, India's approach to Humanitarian assistance is derived from set of principles and priorities derived from the core values of its foreign policy. India criticizes aid from Western donors and organizations as "supply driven" and accuses them of carelessly providing aid. India strives to adopt a strictly non-political approach to humanitarian assistance, stressing that humanitarian aid should not be linked to political objectives and identifies humanitarian assistance from Western donors as political. But it may also concluded that India's humanitarian assistance strategy is also determined by the political factors for making good relations with other developing countries in order to gain support for permanent seat in the United Nations Security council and by economic factors to gain access to new markets and raw materials.

Development in the Indian economy with the availability of greater financial resources in hand , the presence of a large Indian Diaspora in various parts of the world and its remittances, and a growing sense of international responsibilities has augmented India's position as an aid giver in the last few years.

Between 2000 and 2015 according to the Asia Foundation, India's development assistance has grown sevenfold. India has earned the requisite experience and expertise to help other nations to deal with disastrous situations. The Indian government humanitarian assistance activities are extended in cases of cyclones, droughts, earthquakes or floods and this policy is in contrast with the conception of Western donors which also include 'helping civilian population affected by armed conflicts. India also needs to evaluate aid modalities to preclude negative consequences and should articulate the government's policy on humanitarian assistance. India should take a seat at the table of multilateral organisations and shape the international humanitarian system from within instead of criticising it from outside.

Notes

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